

National and International Environmental Law and Justice

The Unresolved Issues

1. Human Environmental Rights

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1. Human Environmental Rights

Among the many unresolved issues in International Environmental Law that arise, no doubt the one associated with Human Environmental Rights, or Environmental Human Rights, as both of these interrelated terms are commonly used, has caused more controversies in recent times. While some believe it should be a basic human right, others argue such a right cannot be purely human-centered, but include the broader concept of right to a safe natural environment within the ecological and ecosystems context.

The necessity for such a right goes back into the history of efforts to establish human rights, and the Charter of the United Nations, and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the General Assembly in 1945 and 1948 respectively have gradually been expanded to encompass other specific human-centered standards and rights. Human rights basically include the right to life and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and the right to education, and many more. Everyone is legally entitled to these rights without discrimination. There are thus three overarching types of human rights norms: civil-political, socio-economic, and collective-developmental.

The first two rights, which represent potential claims of individual persons against the state, are firmly accepted norms identified in international treaties and conventions. However, the inclusion of other fundamental human rights called for are still at the stage of discussions and debate, one being Human Environmental Rights. Environmental rights should be by definition an extension of the basic human rights that mankind requires and deserves. In addition to the right to food, clean water, suitable shelter, and education, right to a safe and sustainable natural environment is paramount as all other rights are dependent upon it, and as aptly defined by Friends of the Earth International (2003):

Environmental rights mean access to the unspoiled natural resources that enable survival, including land, shelter, food, water and air. They also include more purely ecological rights, including the right for a certain beetle to survive or the right for an individual to enjoy an unspoiled landscape.....Environmental rights are human rights, as people's livelihoods, their health, and sometimes their very existence depend upon the quality of and their access to the surrounding environment as well as the recognition of their rights to information, participation, security and redress.

However, even if historical records show that the relationship between human rights and the environment was first recognized by the UN General Assembly as early as during the late 1960s, bringing it up to the forefront has been a long, strenuous and mostly unsuccessful exercise. The initial efforts started in 1972, when the direct relationship between the environment and the right to life was recognized at the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (Stockholm, 1972) through its 26 principles. The Preamble to the Stockholm Declaration states that:

Man is both creature and moulder of his environment, which gives him physical sustenance and affords him the opportunity for intellectual, moral, social and spiritual growth. Both aspects of man's environment, the natural and the manmade, are essential to his well-being and to the enjoyment of basic human rights - even the right to life itself.

Principle 1 of the Declaration establishes a further foundation for linking human rights and environmental protection, declaring that:

Man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being.

The Stockholm Declaration of 1972 further informs that procedural human rights are emphasized in several environmental agreements. Numerous international treaties adopted since the Stockholm Conference call upon states to take specific measures to ensure that the public is adequately informed about environmental risks, including health risks, posed by specific activities. In addition to the right to information, the public is also given broad rights of participation in decision-making and access to remedies for environmental harm. Among the many international agreements utilizing procedural human rights to achieve better environmental protection in order to protect human health, the Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters, the Aarhus, Convention of 1998, stands out and leads the way as a model of environmental democracy.

As a result of the 1972 Conference, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) was set up to shoulder the responsibility of environmental matters, but not so much that of environmental law and justice.

A decade after Stockholm, the 1982 World Charter for Nature acknowledges that:

Mankind is a part of nature and life depends on the uninterrupted functioning of natural systems which ensure the supply of energy and nutrients.

About three decades later, after some in-depth work and consultations, the Earth Charter (2000) came into being, but not into any form of legal prescription, recommending that
.....environmental protection, human rights, equitable human development, and peace are interdependent and indivisible.

It appears that Charters never really carried the real weights of Charters, but were meant to be guideline documents that would quickly be forgotten.

Two decades after Stockholm, the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (also known as the Earth Summit/the Rio Declaration-UNCED, 1992) switches the issue from an environmental one to one related to development, stating in Principle 1:

Human beings are at the centre of concerns for sustainable development. They are entitled to a healthy and productive life in harmony with nature.

Interestingly, Principle 4 switches the argument back to putting the environment at the forefront and as a prerequisite to development, establishing that:

In order to achieve sustainable development, environmental protection shall constitute an integral part of the development process and cannot be considered in isolation from it.

UNCED was more concerned about development, which can be defined as purely an exercise only concerned with economic development through the exploitation of resources; and even if the word or rather concept '*sustainable*' was added to development it did not make it anymore palatable to the concept of environmental protection as an addition to the rights of people (human rights). Analysing the UNCED policy direction/directive, the Director General of the World Health Organization (WHO, 1999), Dr. Gro Harlem Brundtland found it important to come up with a conclusion that points in the right direction:

As long as health is seen as the responsibility of the health authorities alone, and not the shared responsibility of individuals, communities, employers, and all government agencies at all levels, sustainable development remains a lofty goal.

In regional systems, both the African Charter (1986) and the Protocol of San Salvador (1988) came into being to address the connectivity between human rights and the environment. Under the African system, the African Commission took a landmark decision in 2001 with regard to the right to a clean environment, by emphasising that the right to a clean and safe environment is critical to the enjoyment of economic, social and cultural rights. This right, it was held, requires a state to take reasonable measures to prevent pollution and ecological degradation, to promote conservation and to secure an ecologically sustainable development and use of natural resources.

The Commission stated that compliance with the right to a clean environment must include undertaking or at least permitting independent scientific monitoring of threatened environments, and requiring and publicising environmental and social impact studies prior to any major industrial development. This right also requires that appropriate monitoring is undertaken, information is disseminated to the communities exposed to hazardous materials and situations, and that meaningful opportunities are guaranteed for individuals to be heard and to participate in development decisions affecting their communities.

Article 24 of the African Charter (1986) and Article 11 of the Protocol of San Salvador (1988) explicitly address the right to a healthy environment. Article 24 of the African Charter states that:

All peoples shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development.

Article 11 of the Protocol of San Salvador refers to a '*right to a healthy environment*' and states that:

Everyone shall have the right to live in a healthy environment and to have access to basic public services.

And as such, states '*shall promote the protection, preservation and improvement of the environment.*' While it was deemed necessary to have separate statutes dealing with human rights in a few countries, a number of others have had these same rights embodied in their constitutions. However, what has always been omitted in such statements is that the majority of the poorer states, mainly in the South, are legally powerless against the more powerful states of the North and particularly against powerful corporations that most the time have the

lobbying capacity to turn international environmental laws and agreements in their favour, or simply flaunt them.

On the International scene, the concept of human environmental rights has not remained a new concept or philosophy that needs endless debating, although most of the time it has and still remains as such, since several international agreements after the 1972 UN Stockholm Conference have discussed it extensively but not necessarily exhaustively, with some 60 nations ensuring this right through their constitutions or legislation. The concept was further stimulated through the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED, 1992) and the 2001 meeting of the UN Commission on Human Rights (UNCHR, 2001), which also called for an international seminar to discuss the issue, and innumerable UN-sponsored discussions that have taken place during the last decades, with some still ongoing.

Since the U.N. Conference on the Human Environment in 1972, a number of countries have incorporated the right to a healthy environment into their national constitutions, in varying formulations that are mostly theoretically administrative rather than based on environmental law. In a move to tow the line rather than lead the way on the international platform, four decades after the 1972 Stockholm declaration the UN-OHCHR (2012) declares that:

All human beings depend on the environment in which we live. A safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment is integral to the full enjoyment of a wide range of human rights, including the rights to life, health, food, water and sanitation.

Human environmental rights cannot be simply regarded as a national issue while it is actually an international issue within existing human rights and international environmental laws, even though those international organisations purportedly responsible for frameworking international human and environmental laws went into a period of dormancy for several decades.

The situation does not appear to have changed since. In other words, The Rio Declaration never considered human environmental rights as a deeper human connection and association with the natural environment on which humanity depends, but rather as connected to the unnatural process of economic development. The best that the Rio Declaration could do was to re-iterate the basics of human rights elements already established by the Human Rights Commission. Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development states that:

For the effective enjoyment of human rights including, inter alia, the right to life, the right to adequate food, the right to the highest attainable standard of health, the right to adequate housing, the right to self-determination and human rights obligations related to access to safe drinking water and sanitation, and recalling that in no case may a people be deprived of its own means of subsistence.

However, to this day there has been no consensus reached as to whether environmental rights should be included into the human rights statute, and what appropriate legal tools would be in place for enforcement.

Almost three decades after RIO the situation, rather than improving, has worsened, with the major international organisations still arguing about how to complicate the issue of rights even further, while actors from the business sector have accelerated their agenda on environmental and human rights degradation through their uncontrolled activities. Industries and Multinational Companies play an increasingly large role in the world, and are responsible

for a large number of human and environmental rights abuses. Although the legal and moral environment surrounding the actions of governments is reasonably well developed, that surrounding multinational companies is both controversial and ill-defined.

Multinational companies' primary responsibility is to their shareholders, not to those affected by their actions. Such companies may be larger than the economies of some of the states within which they operate, and can wield significant economic and political power. Apart from some non-enforceable guidelines and codes of conduct, no international treaties, especially in the form of hard laws, exist to specifically regulate the behaviour of companies with regard to human environmental rights, and national legislation can be either very variable., or purposely flexible.

But rather than progress from the 1972 Conference, several events, especially in the field of enforcement of international agreements, appear to have been actually either delayed or stopped in their progression. Since 1972 many problems have worsened. Both Agenda 21 (UNCED-1992) and the later UNCED Conventions up till the Santiago Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC-2019) stepped in with new frameworks in an attempt to encourage or induce implementation of some of the post Stockholm agreements, but failed to influence national policies and curtail activities leading to unsustainable growth. Laws and strategies intended to support the mainstreaming of sustainable development have had little impact in most countries, while processes encouraging perverse resource exploitation and use remain still widespread and often unchecked. The many non-mandatory (*soft law*) treaties and guidelines that appeared, including the Rio agreements, proved to be inadequate for effective control of these processes. These failures have led to calls for a new approach, one that ensures compliance, either voluntarily through existing agreements and guideline, or through the application of hard laws.

In 1997 UNESCO adopted the Declaration on the Responsibilities of the Present Generation towards the Future Generation. Article 1 of the declaration states:

The present generations have the responsibility of ensuring that the needs and interests of present and future generations are fully safeguarded.

But what UNESCO omits to consider is that if the present generation does not have rights and the tools to enforce those rights so as to safeguard the needs and interest of future generations, then Article1 becomes simply a vague assumption.

The preamble to the UNESCO's declaration states that '*at this point in history, the very existence of humankind and its environment are threatened,*' and the declaration covers a variety of issues including:

- Protection of the environment,
- The human genome,
- Biodiversity,
- Cultural heritage,
- Peace,
- Development, and
- Education.

Interestingly, UNESCO's reference to the '*responsibilities of the present generations towards future generations*' also appears in several international reports and instruments, prior the UNESCO's declaration, and have been extensively discussed at several international events, including:

- The Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage (UNESCO-1972).
- The Brundtland Commission's Report (1987) *Our Common Future*.
- The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD - Rio de Janeiro, 1992).
- The Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (UN Conference on Environment and Development, UNCED, 1992).
- The Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action (World Conference on Human Rights, 1993).
- The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC-1994).
- The Kyoto Protocol (1997).

In a declaration in 2001, Claus Toepfer, then Executive Director of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), reflected in a statement made at the 57th Session of the Commission on Human Rights to the effect that:

Human rights cannot be secured in a degraded or polluted environment. The fundamental right to life is threatened by soil degradation and deforestation and by exposures to toxic chemicals, hazardous wastes and contaminated drinking water. Environmental conditions clearly help to determine the extent to which people enjoy their basic rights to life, health, adequate food and housing, and traditional livelihood and culture. It is time to recognize that those who pollute or destroy the natural environment are not just committing a crime against nature, but are violating human rights as well.

Toepfer acknowledges there is violation of human rights, but what is lacking from the statement is reference to a clause, or clauses in the Human Rights statute that are being violated and whether tools or instruments have been put in place for legal redressment of such transgressions. Further questions that may arise regard the connection between human rights and environmental rights in the pursuit of a solution to these problems.

In 2002, the World Summit on Sustainable Development in South Africa (WSSD 2002) merely acknowledged the position that there exists a possible relationship between the natural environment and human rights. In addition, the UN Human Rights Commission adopted several resolutions linking human rights and the environment, such as Res. 2005/60 associating Human rights and the environment as part of sustainable development. The resolution called on states to:

Take all necessary measures to protect the legitimate exercise of everyone's human rights when promoting environmental protection and sustainable development and reaffirmed, in this context that everyone has the right, individually and in association with others, to participate in peaceful activities against violations of human rights and fundamental freedoms.

The onset of new environmental issues, especially pollution, climate change and global warming, have but added to the conflicts between different human rights. Ultimately, human rights should principally be about healthy and performing ecosystems, thereby a healthy environment, but one stumbling block is that the responsibilities of multinational corporations, so far relatively unaddressed by human rights legislations, and that should be of paramount consideration, has been left out of the equation, the concentration being mainly on states, which in turn rely on the goodwill and behaviour of their political leaders.

A number of UN General Assembly and other International Resolutions and Treaties relating to the protection of the global climate and the environment, including pollution, for present and future generations have been also been adopted since 1990, but all denying people the right to access the necessary tools to enforce protection.

Presently, there is no universal human right to water, binding or not, enshrined by the United Nations or any other multilateral body. However, in November 2002, the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ECOSOC-2002) issued a non-binding comment affirming that access to water was a human right, stating:

The human right to water is indispensable for leading a life in human dignity. It is a prerequisite for the realization of other human rights.

Between 1972 and 2019, there have been endless meetings and resolutions, and, starting from The Stockholm Declaration of 1972, through to The Nairobi Declaration of 1982, The World Charter for Nature of 1982, The Earth Summit of 1992, The Johannesburg Conference on Sustainable Development (WSSD) in 2002, The UN Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012 (RIO+20), and through the many other meetings and resolutions of the UN.HRC, the UN.OHCHR, WHO, OECD, UNECE, UNEP, ECOSOC, the UNFCCC and the UN, some of the outcomes of the worrying state of the world community have been examined, and the position of humans and environmental rights discussed, and commented upon, giving rise to innumerable resolutions all repeating the same theme, with some variations, but never addressing the core of the issue. It has been a long road with many statements and realisations, but getting nowhere to firmly establish human environmental rights within the framework of human rights laws.

Article 12 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) states that:

The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health.

Article 2(b) therein provides that:

The steps to be taken by the States Parties to the present Covenant to achieve the full realization of this right shall include those necessary for the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene.

A 2009 report for the Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights (OHCHR-2009) emphasizes the key point that:

While the universal human rights treaties do not refer to a specific right to a safe and healthy environment, the United Nations human rights treaty bodies all recognize the intrinsic link between the environment and the realization of a range of human rights, such as the right to life, to health, to food, to water, and to housing’.

Arguably, such rights may be there, but mechanisms for enforcement are not.

Early in 2011 the UN Human Rights Council (UN.HCR (2011) initiated a study of the relationship between human rights and the environment, which led to the 2012 appointment of an independent expert, to make recommendations on human rights obligations relating to the enjoyment of a ‘*safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment*’. Mr. John H. Knox was appointed to the position in August 2012. In his first report (A/HRC/22/43), presented to the Council in March 2013, he emphasized that human rights and the environment are interdependent.

Mr Knox summarized in his second report, (A/HRC/25/53), presented in March 2014, that virtually every source reviewed identified human rights enjoyment were being infringed or threatened by environmental harm. In his subsequent report to the Human Rights Council (A/HRC/28/61), presented in March 2015, he described more than 100 good practices that should be adopted to protect human environmental rights. In March 2015, in its resolution 28/11, the Human Rights Council decided to extend the mandate for another three years. The rapporteur, Mr Knox, submitted reports on specific aspects of the relationship between human rights and the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment, including climate change and human rights, in 2016 (A/HRC/31/52), biodiversity and human rights in 2017 (A/HRC/34/49), and children's rights and the environment in 2018 (A/HRC/37/58).

Seven years down the road, the conclusion of the UN.HRC's report (A/73/188) of Rapporteur John Knox reveals three of the eternal subjects of discussions that have led to nowhere, and probably never will unless a different route is taken. These three salient points of the conclusion include:

1. The relationship between human rights and the environment has evolved rapidly over the past five decades, and even more so over the past five years. The '*greening*' of well-established human rights, including the rights to life, health, food, water, housing, culture, development, property and home and private life, has contributed to improvements in the health and well-being of people across the world.
2. There can be no doubt that the right to a healthy environment is a moral right, essential to the health, well-being and dignity of all human beings. However, to ensure that this right is respected, protected and fulfilled, it requires legal protection.
3. Given the importance of clean air, safe water, healthy ecosystems and a stable climate to the ability of both current and future generations to lead healthy and fulfilling lives, global recognition of the right to a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment should be regarded as a human right.

The word '*greening*' in the conclusions of the report has been emphasized, as one that has no know definition, but commonly used by businesses recently to indicate their intention to respect and protect the natural environmental, a highly controversial and debatable projection of the business image.

Existing international human rights law, environmental laws, and economic laws have no provisions for legal actions from victims of environmental destruction. Neither do current international laws provide for legal action in case of environmental harm to individuals; any such action must be connected to a substantive right, a requirement that renders courts or commissions powerless. To comprehend how even when corporations have been endowed with the legality of personhood together with the associated responsibilities and liabilities, and yet ignore these responsibilities and liabilities is beyond the understanding of reasonable citizens.

As a strategy to fill the void left by hard-law approaches that were applicable in the past, the UN decided to give the '*partnership approach*' a chance, launching the Global Compact (UN-GC) in 2000 as a soft-law strategy for '*leveraging the platform*' of large corporations and encouraging socially responsible corporate behaviour. The GC, just like the earlier UN Norms (1997), covers broad and flexible principles that hinge upon existing UN documents, namely the UDHR and the Rio Declaration.

The UN's Global Compact, a purely voluntary coalition formed by nearly fifty corporate charter members to promote human rights and environmental standards within businesses, and which could benefit environmental human rights generally in the long term, recommends that corporations:

1. Support a precautionary approach to environmental challenges,
2. Undertake initiatives to promote greater environmental responsibility, and
3. Encourage the development and diffusion of environmentally friendly technologies.

However, if the movement for environmental human rights continues to gain ground, then the connection created by the Global Compact between the UN and businesses could be affected positively. First of all, environmental human rights, however, whenever and wherever manifested, would have greater international legal significance under customary international law, and that could make it harder for TNC's environmental violations to go unnoticed, even if TNCs are supposedly not legally bound to international law, and the implications have been discussed by Shaughnessy (2000).

It is interesting to note that an earlier UNHRC project to adopt a declaration on human rights and the environment terminated in 1994 with a report and the text of a declaration that failed to secure the backing of states, and trying to find reasons why may lead to other areas that remain unexplored.

However, it has been established through numerous meetings, declarations and studies that the right to health includes an array of factors, including a healthy natural environment, with healthy and performing ecosystems that contribute to a healthy life. The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1985), the body responsible for monitoring the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights refers to these as the '*underlying determinants of health*'. They include, amongst others healthy environmental conditions. The UN.HRC (2005) also adopted Resolution 2005/60 (2005) on human rights and the environment, again, declaring its intentions to:

1. Take note of the report of the Secretary-General on human rights and the environment as part of sustainable development (E/CN.4/2005/96);
2. Reaffirm that peace, security, stability and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, including the right to development, as well as respect for cultural diversity are essential for achieving sustainable development and ensuring that sustainable development benefits all, as set forth in the Plan of Implementation of the World Summit on Sustainable Development;
3. Call upon States to take all necessary measures to protect the legitimate exercise of everyone's human rights when promoting environmental protection and sustainable development;
4. Stress the importance for States, when developing their environmental policies, to take into account how environmental degradation may affect all members of society, and in particular women, children, indigenous people or disadvantaged members of society; and
5. Encourage all efforts towards the implementation of the principles of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, in particular principle 10, in order to contribute, inter alia, to effective access to judicial and administrative proceedings, including redress and remedy.

What the UN.HCR (2005) does is much more behaving as an observer rather than a proactive organisation with the power to advise, institute actions and provide for the power of execution. Still swimming in safe waters and repeating what has already been observed, analysed, and discussed, in 2011 the UN.HCR (2011) recognises the existence of at least three more pillars that may enhance human environmental rights, and this time associated with the activities of corporations:

1. The state's continuing duty to protect human rights against abuses by business;
2. The responsibility of corporations to respect human rights through the use of due diligence; and
3. Individual access to remedy: governments must ensure that where human rights are harmed by business activities there is adequate accountability and effective redress, whether judicial or non-judicial.

Moving from one recommendation to another, and one decision to another, in its Final Activity Report on Human Rights and the Environment, The Council of Europe (2005) declares that what constitutes a decent environment is a human value judgement, that is not a measurable one, on which reasonable people will differ, and that policies should be central to choices and context in considering:

What weight should be given to natural resource exploitation over nature protection, to industrial development over air and water quality, to land-use development over conservation of forests and wetlands, to energy consumption over the risks of climate change, and so on?

These choices, rather than necessities, may result in wide diversities of policy and interpretation, as different governments and international organizations pursue their own priorities and make their own value judgements, moderated only to some extent by international agreements on such matters as climate change and the conservation of biological diversity, without neglecting the ethical viewpoints on such matters. The assumption is that all humans are not equal. Prioritising development over environment, as appears to be the case in all discussions and recommendations so far, throws the environmental human rights issue ever further down the list of immediate actions.

Taking the discussion even further, the International Law Association-ILC (2006) pointed out a number of issues that need consideration:

1. Any state which allows harmful activities within its own territory to cause foreseeable harm extraterritorially is likely to violate human rights obligations if it does not permit access to justice and afford effective domestic remedies.
2. It would be reasonable to expect one state to take into account foreseeable transboundary impacts in another.
3. Where it is possible to take effective measures to prevent or mitigate transboundary harm to human rights, the argument of no obligation cannot be entertained.
4. It may be better to recognise that human rights law is not the right medium for addressing a shared problem.

The ILC mentions issues that need to be addressed, with no further efforts to resolve these issues. Neither does the ILC examine such issues as associated with the activities of TNCs.

Voluntary Codes of Conduct and Corporate Accountability have been a growing trend amongst TNCs, more of a fashion than a genuine intent of responsible behaviours in most instances. While there is an ongoing debate as to the effectiveness of such voluntary codes, however, the question often asked is: can these trends affect and improve corporate

accountability? Corporations have yet to be signatories to binding international instruments, since they often play a significant role in the destruction and degradation of the environment, which in turn harms human communities.

Much earlier, Eaton (1997) discussed the drawbacks of existing sets of only voluntary guidelines for international businesses, one such set being the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UN-OHCHR, 2011), which instruct corporations to respect human rights but leaves enforcement in the hands of states. More recently Corporate Human Rights Benchmark (CHRB-2020) became yet another newly established research initiative supposedly concerned with the impact of businesses on human rights, but in his analysis, Eaton (1997) rightly emphasized on how Multinationals easily avoid prosecution because no international legal framework exists to hold them accountable, and such legal frameworks still do not exist. As such, under current international law, TNCs are not liable for environmental destruction or associated human rights abuses.

Regarding lawsuits against corporations, shortly after the Exxon-Valdez spill in (1989), the Coalition for Environmentally Responsible Economies Principles (CERES) realised in 1989, and further affirmed by Smith (1993) that:

The existing legal regime, with its convoluted system of suits and counter suits, can neither adequately hold corporations publicly accountable for their actions nor respond to environmental disasters with the immediacy necessary to contain such crises.

The impression is that corporations are above the law, but that is not simply because of their status and power, but rather because legal frameworks are inadequate to control them.

It is also important to note that even the rapid development of environmental jurisprudence in Europe has resulted in the consistent rejection of proposals for an environmental protocol to be added to the ECHR. And up till 2010, the Committee of Ministers were again persisting in not adding a right to a healthy and viable environment to the ECHR. There is no doubt that there has been a strong lobby to protect businesses, and profit at the cost of wanton environmental destruction, and ignoring basic human rights.

To further efforts in establishing an environmental human rights platform of discussion, Professor John Ruggie (2008; 2011a,b; 2013) developed the UN Framework on Business and Human Rights (UNFGBHR-2008), operationalizing it through a set of '*Guiding Principles*' on business and human rights (UN-OHCHR, 2011). Both initiatives were endorsed unanimously by the Human Rights Council (HRC-2011a) and rest upon three pillars: '*Protect, Respect and Remedy*' human rights. Such sweeping broad plans, rather than strategies, appear to have added little to efforts to acknowledge the necessity of legal instruments to protect environmental human rights. However, the '*Ruggie Process*' discussed by López (2013), tends to shift the legal obligations of businesses into yet another business white elephant termed '*Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)*.' To this day CSR policies and objectives, or the concept of '*Sustainable Development*,' the backbone of UN discussions, have added little if nothing to environmental protection, environmental rights or environmental justice.

There are concerns over using the existing human rights framework to enforce environmental rights. First, there is little jurisprudence on the rights that are implicated by environmental problems or the standards by which such environmental violations should be measured. This is not a hindrance to the theory, but rather means that proponents will have to continue to push for a connection between existing human rights and environmental damage.

But what is clearly visible in the Ruggie's draft and previous ones is the treatment of human environmental rights as subsidiary or secondary to the rights of businesses, thus giving businesses the upper hand once more on human environmental rights. It is also interesting to note that the UN-HCR discussed such issues previously (UN-HRC/OHCHR, 2011; UN-HRC, 2016; UN-HRC, 2018), and nothing substantial or substantive came of these discussions apart from vague recommendations.

A final draft on the relationship between human rights and the environment has been produced and published by the UN (UN-HRC, 2020); however, the outcome is to be discussed yet. There is also a need to be reminded that the UN-HRC started discussions on the issue as early as 2011 under the '*Protect, Respect and Remedy Framework*' (UN-HRC, 2011b; d). And no consensus appears to have been reached a decade later, and it is likely that stagnation will continue to plague efforts.

And in spite of some timid progress made at the international level, Boyle (2012a) still have reservations, about persisting problems, stating that:

Despite their evolutionary character, human rights treaties still fall short of guaranteeing a right to a decent or satisfactory environment if that concept is understood in broader, essentially qualitative terms unrelated to impacts on specific humans.

For this purpose the role of international human rights courts is important but limited to the protection of individual civil and political rights and ill-suited to broader forms of public interest litigation for which national courts are better equipped, but not in cases of transboundary breach of human rights.

While there is still no explicit universally accepted right to a healthy environment, seven landmark international instruments link human rights and environmental protection, including:

1. The Stockholm Declaration/Stockholm Agreement on the Human Environment (1972), which explicitly recognize the link between the environment and human rights, granting nations the '*sovereign right to exploit their own resources pursuant to their own environmental policies*', including the '*fundamental right to freedom, equality, and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being, and responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations.*'
2. The Declaration of the Right to Development, UN-OHCHR (1986), which includes equality of access to basic resources and food.
3. Article 24 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted in 1990 (UN-OHCHR, 1990) links environmental quality to the right to health.
4. The Rio Declaration's (1992) Principle 4 that states environmental protection cannot be considered in isolation from the development process.
5. The Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters (Aarhus, 1998),
6. The Draft Declaration of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, UN-UNDRIP (2007) that recognizes '*distinctive and profound relationship with their lands*' and includes '*the prevention and redress for dispossession of their lands, territories, or resources.*'
7. The UN Draft Declaration of Principles on Human Rights and the Environment (UN-OHCHR, 2018)
8. The Hague Declaration (2019) that recognizes '*the right to live in dignity in a viable global environment.*'

To extend the same spirit to the international level, the Bali Guidelines (UNEP 2015) followed to re-enforce Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration, reaffirming that:

States shall facilitate and encourage public awareness and participation by making information widely available.

UNEP, however, fails to create the necessary instruments to guide States liable within the global context, and thus failing again to move the talk into meaningful policies for action. As much as the Human Rights Charter, to be meaningful Environmental Human Rights must also be an international effort.

Several international treaties adopted since the Stockholm Conference call upon states to take specific measures to ensure that the public is adequately informed about environmental risks, including health risks, posed by specific activities. In addition to the right to information, the public is also given broad rights of participation in decision-making and access to remedies for environmental harm. The protections afforded have increased in scope and number since the adoption of Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, but it is also interesting to note the summary of the 2011 UN-OHCHR Report, which states:

Human rights obligations and commitments have the potential to inform and strengthen international, regional and national policymaking in the area of environmental protection and promoting policy coherence, legitimacy and sustainable outcomes

But have they in practical terms?

Where the world has reached to this day, in both recommendations and actions, appear to have left too many voids in International Environmental Law, and the will to palliate those voids have not been forthcoming. From the 1948 Human Rights Declaration through to the 1972 Stockholm Conference, all international discussions have simply acknowledged that humanity has fundamental rights over the environment that constitutes its living habitat, but most have been evasive as to the issue of Human Environmental Rights being a legal right, protected both in enforceable national and international law. Acknowledgement, which has been the case so far, does not necessarily means acceptance. There is therefore a need to analyse and discuss the Environmental Human Rights issue, as well as several other issues omitted or neglected in International Environmental Law and Legislations.

However, to this day there has been no consensus reached as to whether environmental rights should be included into the human rights statute, and what appropriate legal tools are in place for enforcement. In 2019, UNEP and the UN Human Rights Office signed a new agreement, stepping up commitment to protect the human right to a healthy environment, and the Executive Director of UNEP, Inger Andersen, declared at the signing ceremony in Geneva that:

A healthy environment is vital to fulfilling our aspiration to ensure people everywhere live a life of dignity. We must curb the emerging trend of intimidation and criminalisation of land and environmental defenders, and the use of anti-protest and anti-terrorism laws to criminalise the exercise of rights that should be constitutionally protected.

What the director of UNEP said was not much different from what was declared in 1972 at Stockholm, or what has been repeated over and over since. However, UNEP's declaration has thrown in another dimension: the constitutional one. But the central point of all these conferences, discussions, and resolutions is that ignoring the environment in the short term may leave long term deleterious effects on humanity, through the violation of human rights.

The resolution emphasized the needs of the vulnerable members of society and also encouraged efforts towards the implementation of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, another instance of mere acknowledgement of the Environmental Human Rights issue. After almost four decades of discussions, the realisation is that the situation remains unresolved, and has to be taken up through different channels.

What has been of interest, and a subject of discussions recently is the acceptance of social and environmental norms as guidelines to regulate human behaviour. According to Finnemore and Sikkink (1998), norms are generally understood as '*standards of appropriate behaviour for actors with a given identity.*' Emerging from collectively held ideas and expectations, as well as from repeated behaviour, norms have both regulatory and constitutive dimensions. Acharya (2004) discusses how when an increasing number of actors conform to a new norm, it becomes internalized. Thus, for any international norm to spread, external influence, persuasion as well as localisation should be considered as variables in the reception of new norms.

There can further be two distinct approaches to environmental human rights, the anthropocentric or the ecocentric, as previously discussed by Cuomo (1993) and Nickel (1993). While the anthropocentric approach is purely human-centred, protecting humans from environmental harms without consideration for the harms caused to the environment by human activities that eventually affects humans and human rights. The eco-centric view requires that environmental law follows a course in its development geared towards protecting the environment beyond human needs, and requiring that not only should the environment be protected by the advancement of human rights, it should also be protected for its own sake. However, and according to Taylor (1998; 2010) and Mowery (2001) most developments in international law have centered on an anthropocentric approach, the ecological approach being beyond likelihood of succeeding in the near future. That is partly because a greater conflict exists between economic self determination and ecological rights, rather than environmental human rights.

It must also be remembered that human environmental rights does not only ensure that humans have a right to a clean and healthy environment with access to environmental goods and services, but also the inherent right to protect the environment they depend on. In that context the Pachamama Alliance (2008) associates the protection and access to natural resources as a basic necessity to ensure human environmental rights that should be of international concern, stating that:

Environmental Rights are the protection of natural resources; the access to and use of natural resources; and how the access to and use of these resources affects surrounding populations, as well as the resources themselves.

The Pachamama Alliance (2008) also stresses on environmental rights and the right to water:

Environmental rights are an extension of the basic human rights that mankind requires and deserves. In addition to having the right to food, clean water, suitable shelter, and education, having a safe and sustainable environment is paramount as all other rights are dependent upon it. The desire to ensure access for all of Earth's inhabitants to this essential standard of living is the primary concern of environmental rights.

An inability, or unwillingness to settle one single issue about human environmental rights, in this case water, points to the difficult problem of recognising the many other issues associated with environmental human rights.

The persistent view held by most that environmental protection is closely associated with development, and the coining of the term '*sustainable development*' to infer some form of reconciliation between development and environment has been extensively discussed, but has failed to produce the appropriate formula for protection of the human environment. How development, sustainable or not, contribute to environmental and human rights is still a controversial subject.

Discussing environmental and human rights in relation to sustainable development, and in apprehension of the outcome of the 2002 WSSD Conference in South Africa, Adebowale et al. (2001) observe that:

The lack of success of many Rio initiatives makes it appropriate to consider new approaches, which should be rooted in recognition of an inalienable right to a safe and healthy environment.

Adebowale et al. further suggest the following measures to achieve the goal of recognising human environmental rights:

1. Ratify the Aarhus Convention (UNECE, (1998) as an important step to recognising all people's environmental human rights issues;
2. Recognise the need for a strong global commitment to environmental rights as an essential element in efforts to realise sustainable development;
3. Support calls for discussions at WSSD (2002) on the negotiation of a UN Convention on sustainable development and human rights, and engage in dialogue with civil society and other governments on what this should entail; and
4. Emphasise that the rights-based approach, founded on principles of equity, is central to sustainable development, and provides an important means by which to counter the negative impacts of economic and social globalisation.

The authors stressed on the rights-based approach, as opposed to the conventional treaty-based approaches that have failed to have any impact so far. However, and most unfortunately, WSSD 2002 concluded with some meaningful statements to add to the many existing ones, without any concrete policies for improving the plights of both humans and the environment, but again laying emphasis on development, this time around about its connection to poverty reduction. As rightly put by Adebowale et al. (2001) the Aarhus Convention (UNECE, (1998) should be an appropriate tool and an important step to recognising all people's environmental human rights issues, given its nature suitable for international application. UNECE (2000) rightly states that:

Although regional in scope, the significance of the Aarhus Convention is global. It is the most ambitious venture in the area of '*environmental democracy*' so far undertaken under the auspices of the United Nations.

Why the UN kept following different routes that have so far led to no concrete conclusions, rather than use the Aarhus Convention as an anchor is difficult to comprehend. Discussing the inferred human rights to a healthy environment so often found in UN documents, Giorgetta (2002) concludes that:

The right to a healthy environment may be part of existing international law being implemented through human rights instruments. The procedural aspect of the right to a healthy environment embodies the right to information, the right to participate and the right to effective remedies. Participation in the decision-making process and available and effective means of redress are essential features of the right to a healthy environment.

In other words, discussing the rights of parties affected without such parties actually participating in such discussions would lead nowhere.

In her analysis of the Stockholm Conference of 1972, Shelton (2002) points out and discusses the implications of the proclamation of participants at the concluding session implying that *'man is both creature and moulder of his environment'* in the sense that the association of man and his environment has become clear through the statement, and the acceptance of that association as a human right in 1972 should have led to some international instruments that also give man the right of claim and control over that *'environment'* which is *'essential to his well-being and to the enjoyment of basic human right,'* and the mention of the *'right to life itself'* infers the association of the environment to human health. Both statements acknowledge human environmental rights, without, however, attempting to bestow such rights to humans through appropriate binding legislations. Such arguments should also lead to the reflection on and consideration of the rights of the environment that sustains humanity and life on earth, an inter-dependency that is so often neglected.

Shelton (2002) further notes that:

1. Principle 1 of the Stockholm Declaration (1972) establishes a foundation for linking human rights, health, and environmental protection, in its declarations that :
Man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being.
2. Shelton further notes that only two decades after Stockholm did the UN Conference of Rio de Janeiro on Environment and Development in 1992 did the UN decide to formulate, rather than establish. a link between human rights and environmental protection, and that largely in procedural terms, as declared in Principle 10.
3. The author finds that several recent approaches view the links as indivisible and inseparable to be an independent substantive human right, as reflected in paragraph 3 of the Stockholm Declaration (1972), proclaiming that:
Growing evidence of man-made harm in many regions of the earth: dangerous levels of pollution in water, air earth and living beings; major and undesirable disturbances to the ecological balance of the biosphere; destruction and depletion of irreplaceable resources; and gross deficiencies harmful to the physical, mental and social health of man, in the man-made environment, particularly in the living and working environment.

However, the analysis and discussions of Shelton (2002) reveals that no progress has been made in seriously considering curtailing the harms caused to the living and natural environments through re-enforcing human rights to better human living conditions. Rather, there has been an acceleration of environmental destruction leading to environmental injustice, which directly and negatively reflects on the concept of environmental human rights. Shelton remarks that environmental destruction leaves local populations with two basic options:

1. Leave the degraded environment for a more habitable place and become environmental refugees or environmentally displaced people; or
2. Remain in the degraded environment and risk increased morbidity and mortality through exposure to pollution and depleted, degraded, or contaminated food and water sources

What should also receive particular attention is the observation of Steiner et al. (2008) to the effect that:

The environmental dimensions are rarely discussed in general academic treatments of human rights law, where there is almost no debate on the relationship between human rights and the environment.

Steiner et al. (2008) further observe that the environmental dimensions of rights found in several human rights treaties, including the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR-1953) International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR-1966), the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR-1966), the American Convention on Human Rights (AmCHR-1978), and the African Convention on Human and Peoples' Rights (AfCHPR-Banjul-1986) do not more than infer a '*greening*' of existing human rights law rather than the addition of new rights to existing treaties.

Boyle (2012a;b), observing that the relationship between human rights and environmental protection in international law being far from simple or straightforward, examines an attempt to codify and develop international law initiated by the UNHRC in 2011, and concludes that three possibilities should be explored:

1. Procedural rights, an important addition to environmental human rights law, especially for codification.
2. A declaration or protocol could be an appropriate mechanism for articulating in some form the still controversial notion of a right to a decent environment.
3. Resolving the difficult issue of extra-territorial application of existing human rights treaties to transboundary pollution and global climate change, which still remains unaddressed.

Boyle further adds that there is a need for law to be in global terms, treating the global environment and climate as the '*common concern of humanity*,' rendering governments directly accountable for their failure to regulate and control environmental harms and nuisances, including those caused by corporations, and a need for facilitating access to justice and enforcing environmental laws and judicial decisions.

Boyle (2012) bases his arguments on the human rights that are directly affected by the state of the environment consist of but are not limited to the following:

- The right to life,
- The right to an adequate standard of living, and
- The right to health.

Also, procedural human rights such as access to information and participation in decision-making are connected to the right of citizens, and should empower communities to partake in the formulation of environmental policies. However, that is rarely the case, declares Boyle.

From discussions so far, environmental human rights, apart from the right to a clean and safe environment, further encompass two other main areas:

1. The right to act to protect the environment, and
2. The right to information, to access to justice, and to participate in environmental decision-making.

Boyle further comments that the ‘greening’ of existing human rights has already taken place and would add nothing and clarify little, and refers to Lauterpacht (1955) who stated:

Codification which constitutes a record of the past rather than a creative use of the existing materials-legal and others-for the purpose of regulating the life of the community is a brake upon progress.

However, Lauterpacht’s observation was made too far back in time to be a reference for the present time and situations. Such a brake upon progress in the development of human environmental rights were reflected as early as 1949 in a UN-ILC Survey, which concluded that codification may contain significant elements of progressive development and law reform, but contradicts itself by questioning the wisdom of taking the idea further, rather than paving the way for it. A lot of progress would have been since the survey if reason prevailed over assumptions and predictions.

The question that arises is was it not rather premature for Lauterpacht to dismiss codification at a time when human and environmental issues were not as serious and impactful as they are today? However, at the European Level and in an effort to set things right, the Aarhus Convention (1998) establishes a number of rights for individuals and their associations, at national, regional or local levels with regard to environmental human rights, providing for:

1. Access to environmental information,
2. Public participation in environmental decision-making, and
3. Access to justice.

In other words, the inclusion of participatory environmental democratic processes in policy making, which is still a long way away, and still missing in establishing the connection between human rights and the environment. The Convention, however, identifies three theoretical approaches to the relationship between human rights and the environment, similar to what was proposed by Boyle (2012a;b):

1. The environment should be seen as a ‘*precondition to the enjoyment of human rights*’,
2. Human rights should be considered as a ‘*tools to address environmental issues, both procedurally and substantively*’, and
3. The necessity for the integration of human rights and the environment under the concept of sustainable development.

Further, the Convention recognizes that many forms of environmental damage are transnational in character, and that the extraterritorial application of human rights law in this context remains unsettled. It concludes that ‘*further guidance is needed to inform options for further development of the law in this area.*’ So, the waiting time has been extended.

Moreover, Hickey and Mitlin (2009) simultaneously argue that in some cases a human rights-based approach can lead to:

1. Promote non-sustainable use of natural resources, where one group obtains control over natural resources at the expense of one or more other groups;
2. Promote inappropriate governance, because the grant of rights can also be used to secure (increased) power to certain groups at the expense of other (less politically strong) groups.

The fears of Hickey and Mitlin a decade ago was what was exactly happening at that time and still happening today. The objective of environmental human rights should be looked upon as a right of participation in the management of a healthy environment for both human and non-human life, not as a right for appropriation, exploitation and control.

Commenting on why the UN is making no headway on the issue of human environmental rights, Boer (2014) declares that:

The relationship between human rights and environmental protection in international law is far from simple or straightforward, posing some difficult questions about basic principles of human rights law.

Boer further adds that focussing attention on uncontrolled environmental harms may allow legal systems to enforce convention rights while balancing negative aspects of economic development. Referring to the Aarhus convention, Boer concludes that there is the opportunity for the right of access of citizens to information, participation in environmental decisions that affect them, and access to justice for redressment, but hesitations and a lack of goodwill prevent the realisation of such an opportunity at the global level. Or should it be considered as a lack of vision?

Boer's observations and declaration takes the argument back to a meaningful statement from Boyle (2012a):

The merits of any proposal for a declaration or protocol on this subject thus depend on how far it deals with fundamental problems or merely window dresses what we already know. There is little to be said in favour of simply codifying the application of the rights to life, private life and property in an environmental context.

Which makes Boyle (2012a) raise still a further issue associated with Transboundary situations and the statement of the Aarhus Convention:

While the jurisdiction of States is primarily territorial, it may sometimes be exercised outside the national territory. Considering the object and purpose of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, it would seem natural that, even when such is the case, State parties to the Covenant should be bound to comply with its provisions.

Transboundary pollution, which should also include emissions, and global climate change provide the two obvious examples. In general, states have a duty in international law to exercise due diligence over activities within their own territory that may cause significant harm to other states or areas beyond their national jurisdiction, including the global environment, and especially in the case of climate change and its associated risks.. But a 'duty' is hardly a legal obligation.

In an in-depth discourse on '*Human Rights Approach to Environmental Protection*,' Pathak (2014) concludes that:

Environmental protection and human rights are interrelated, interconnected, and mutually responsive as both of them are intended to the well-being of humanity. Safe and healthy environment is the pre-condition for the enjoyment of fundamental human rights.

What should not be omitted in any discussion regarding Human Environmental Rights is that there should not be consideration only for a '*Safe and healthy environment*,' but also a duty for humanity to protect and preserve that environment to keep it both safe and healthy. What should also be considered is that apart from being an issue to be discussed at international, national, organisational or individual levels, human environmental rights is an international issue, both within the context of human rights laws and within the framework of international environmental laws.

According to Pathak, what constitutes a decent environment is a human value judgement, on which the reasoning of people may differ. Policy choices abound in this context and should include:

- Weight that should be given to natural resource exploitation over nature protection,

- Issues regarding prioritising industrial development over air and water quality,
- Land-use development over conservation of forests and wetlands, and
- Energy consumption over the risks of climate change

The list is inexhaustible and remains to be reconciled.

These choices may result in wide diversities of policy and interpretation, as different governments and international organizations pursue their own priorities and make their own value judgements, moderated only to some extent by international agreements on such matters as climate change and the conservation of biological diversity.

There are three ways of establishing human environmental rights, and these have been discussed by Adebowale et al. (2001) and Pathak (2014), namely:

1. Substantive Rights: comprising of civil and political rights, such as the rights to life, freedom of association and freedom from discrimination; economic and social rights such as rights to health, food and an adequate standard of living; cultural rights such as rights to access to religious sites; and collective rights affected by environmental degradation, such as the rights of indigenous peoples.
2. Procedural Rights: prescribing formal steps to be taken in enforcing legal rights, including access to information, public participation, and access to justice.
3. Agreements in the form of hard laws, national and international, where many of these rights, particularly the political ones, are established and enshrined

Discussing the need and necessity for a human right to a healthy environment, Bratspies (2015) declares:

Recognition of the human right to a healthy environment would clarify the obligations that states have vis-à-vis environmental protection. By defining the outer boundaries of the state margin of appreciation to make environmental decisions, such a right would cast violations into sharp relief. Affected individuals would have the opportunity to seek redress through the state courts, as well as to avail themselves of the protection afforded by international tribunals, should state-level remedies prove inadequate.

In a discussion on this issue about what he defines as ‘*human rights technocracy*,’ Taylor (2015) sees it as a form of denial of the intensely political nature of proposals that in effect aims at regulating global capitalism. Taylor concludes that:

If the business and human rights field is something of an epistemic and advocacy ‘*bubble*’ (comprising a relatively small circle of contributors), one risk is that the treaty question is viewed in a fairly technocratic fashion disconnected from clear-eyed acknowledgments about the invariably deeply political nature of any enquiry into regulating business activity globally or locally.

Linda Sheehan and Grant Wilson (2015) of the Earth law Centre establish that human environmental rights revolve mainly around the concept of a human right to a liveable environment, both for present and future generations. The authors recognise at least two basic conceptions of human environmental rights within current human rights systems.

1. The right to a healthy or adequate environment is itself a human right, as stipulate in both Article 21 of the African Charter of Human and People’s Rights, and Article 11 of the San Salvador Protocol to the American Charter of Human Rights.
2. Human environmental rights can be derived from other human rights, usually the right to life, the right to health, the right to private family life, and the right to property as contained in many human rights documents.

Despite these and other escalating climate-related harms, Sheehan and Wilson (2015) find that national and international climate change laws and conventions continue to legalize massive amounts of greenhouse gas emissions while only calling for modest, and usually voluntary, reductions. While the international community fails to address climate change and other drivers of what the authors term ‘*co-violations*’ of human rights, humans and nature continue to suffer the consequences. Finally, sea level rise associated with climate change will affect many millions of people. The inhabitants of sinking islands in the South Seas may justifiably complain of human rights violations, but who is responsible?

- Those states like the UK, US and Germany whose historic emissions have unforeseeably caused the problem?
- Those states like China and India whose current emissions have foreseeably made matters worse? or
- Those states like the US or Canada which have failed to agree to or to take adequate measures to limit further emissions or to stabilise global temperatures at 1990 levels?

The authors define ‘*co-violation*’ of rights as:

A situation in which governments, industries, or others violate both the rights of nature and human rights with the same action.

The discussions of Sheehan and Wilson (2015) elaborate on how the onset of various recent environmental issues, especially climate change, has added to already existing potential conflicts between different human rights. Human rights ultimately require a working and ecosystem and healthy environment, and in the area of environmental human rights, the responsibilities of multinational corporations, so far relatively unaddressed by human rights legislation, should be of paramount and immediate considerations, claim the authors, stating that:

The well-being of humans and nature are inextricably linked. Across the globe, we injure both people and ecosystems by treating the natural world as property to fuel incessant economic growth. These injuries have risen to the level of simultaneous violations, or ‘*co-violations*’, of human rights and nature’s rights.

In their investigation *Fighting for Our Shared Future: Protecting Both Human Rights and Nature’s Rights*, Sheehan and Wilson (2015) of the Earth Law Centre summarise their key findings as:

- Co-violations are frequently connected to the extractive and energy industries.
- Violations of the rights of indigenous peoples and environmental destruction are often strongly associated.
- Co-violations occur globally, but they have been arising more often in the Global South.
- Governments often side with private industry over people and natural systems whose rights may be violated.
- The sources of co-violations are rarely addressed adequately, if they are addressed at all.
- Nature’s rights and human rights are intertwined and co-dependent.

For action by the United Nations and the international community, Sheehan and Wilson (2015) recommend the following:

- Recognize in law and implement the fundamental rights of nature, including through UN General Assembly adoption of the Universal Declaration of the Rights of Mother Earth (UDRME).

- Support swift enforcement of International Rights of Nature Tribunal judgments.
- Create ‘*International Rights of Nature*’ courts to hear cases involving nature’s rights violations.
- Incorporate rights of nature principles into existing human rights instruments and bodies.
- Create an international mechanism to monitor and enforce standards that co-promote human rights and nature’s rights.
- Adopt and implement an international treaty to prevent and enforce against corporate human rights violations.

Voigt and Gant (2015) find that the tendency is leading to a growing body of human rights jurisprudence related to the environment, and UNESCO keeps underlining the necessity to expand and exemplify a human environmental rights approach within legal frameworks. Heiskanen (2018) attributes obvious reasons for international law regimes, state governments, global financial systems, corporate organization of economic life, educational and cultural institutions to having lost their capacity to govern the spheres of human activity for which they are deemed responsible in such a way as to maintain the common good.

Both Voight and Grant (2015) and Shelton (2015) have argued that international environmental law missed the boat, since the decentralisation of environmental law resulted in the creation of hundreds of multilateral environmental agreements supplemented by customary norms, but not the creation of environmental courts or institutions. According to Stephens, (2009), Gearty (2010) and Voight and Grant (2015), since these agreements focus on compliance and facilitation, instead of enforcement and sanctions, there is no strong enforcement mechanism in the form of a judicial body that exercises jurisdiction over the implementation of what they term this ‘*disorderly jumble of treaties.*’

Discussing why States willingly keep the creation of an international environmental court or other international litigation-based compliance mechanisms at bay, Shelton (2015) attributes the same to reservations about the possibility of an expansion of their obligations in terms of future generations and intergenerational equity, and unlimited geographical scope and extraterritorial responsibility. Further, States would also be responsible for harm directly caused by third parties.

The human rights approach to the environment has further raised concerns about the anthropocentrism of the case law, notably among deep ecologists, who claim that the human rights framework is unable to protect the interests of either nature or the environment. However, the development of the green jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR or the Strasbourg Court) has progressed steadily for almost thirty years.

At the global level, there are various United Nations (UN) documents that link human rights and the environment. Shelton (2002) points out and discusses such linkages between human rights and environmental protection, as reflected in the jurisprudence of courts at domestic and international levels. At the domestic level, many countries have integrated a right to a clean environment into their constitutions, and the intricacies and significance of such policy decisions have been discussed by Boyd (2012a) and Gellers (2017).

Similarly, Leib (2011) discusses how the interdependent relationship between human rights and environmental protection is increasingly recognized within international human rights law, as well as in environmental law generally. Leib cites, as examples, the incorporation of a

right to a clean environment in some regional human rights declarations and the requirement of several global environmental treaties that environmental information should be provided to the public. In their discussions, Voigt and Grant (2015) point out how human rights tribunals increasingly face claims of violations stemming from environmental degradation and deprivation, while a growing body of human rights related jurisprudence is emerging with direct legal relevance for both human rights and environmental protection.

Heiskanen (2018) elaborates on the contemporary *corpus* of the ‘green jurisprudence’ of the ECtHR, a well-established case continuum providing protection both for individuals and the environment. For example, and as Heiskanen (2018) points out, the factsheet on the environment and human rights cover seventy-three cases over the period 1990-2016. Regardless of the failure of the Council of Europe to introduce a legal instrument establishing environmental human rights, the ECtHR has been able to ‘green’ several rights of the ECHR. While many argue that in general there is indeed a need to secure formal recognition of the rights protected under the human rights agreements in order to avoid any undemocratic action of the court, no significant criticism has emerged relating to the greening of the rights of the ECHR.

In October 2018, 94 countries drew up a draft text for a binding treaty, which could address the issue of the complex global supply chain that currently makes it difficult to determine who is responsible for environmental damage or human rights violations, and which should also give victims access to justice. Backed by South Africa, Mr. Gallegos (2014, 2018) urged the UN Human Rights Council in Geneva, Switzerland, to immediately begin negotiations to end human rights violations and environmental damage by transnational corporations, with the objective of creating an International Criminal Court for Businesses, further discussed by Crockett et al of Herbert Smith Freehills (2016), and Kyriakakis (2017). The outcome is still pending.

Existing international environmental laws, invariably soft laws, focus on trans-border environmental harm, but do not regulate domestic environmental issues, leaving citizens the option of resorting to national law for redress and protection, not usually an effective avenue. More importantly, international human rights law is neither linked to a healthy environment nor to international environmental law, and Trans National Corporations (TNCs) are not held accountable for human rights violations that stem from their direct or indirect environmental destruction. And yet corporations have been given the rights of personhood, which further ridicules efforts towards further human rights laws.

An open-ended intergovernmental working group (IGWG) with the mandate to elaborate an international legally binding instrument on *Transnational Corporations and Other Business Enterprises* with respect to human rights was subsequently established, with a zero draft produced in 2019 (UN-HCR, 2019) discussed by Lavanga et al. (2019) and further analysed by Lopez (2019), who concludes that:

The revised draft treaty is clearly a welcome and crucial step forward in the process of establishing a legally binding instrument in the field of business and human rights, overcoming most of the most serious – or even the less serious- objections relating to the scope of the treaty and its complementary character in relation to other instruments. There are still many aspects of the treaty and its provisions that require refinement.

Further, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) states that fundamental human rights should include a right to a ‘decent environment,’ notwithstanding

what exactly would be the legal definition of such a ‘*decent environment.*’ Recently, the Framework Principles on Environmental Rights and Obligations (UN-OHCHR, 2018) drafted by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE-2019) supported the universal right to a healthy environment and proposed that the environment should be protected for present and future generations. A number of proposals have also been considered by the Council of Europe to add an environmental right to the European Convention on Human Rights, although none have been implemented so far.

In his report (A/HRC/37/59), the UN Special Rapporteur, Mr. John H. Knox (2018), proposes 16 principles related to human rights and the environment that are based on existing work of the human rights system, of which the following 2 are directly linked to the proposal for recognising environmental human rights:

1. States should ensure a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment in order to respect, protect and fulfil human rights.
2. States should respect, protect and fulfil human rights in order to ensure a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment.

Sending the ball back to the individual States without even having included the finer details of environmental human rights, either within the Human Rights Statute, or as a separate legal Statute appears to be simply shifting responsibilities, especially as at the moment there is no global binding human rights agreement that explicitly recognises the close interconnection between human rights and the environment, let alone a separate human right to a clean or healthy environment. Instead, most human rights bodies make use of an interpretative strategy: they apply existing human rights to environmental issues, and environmentally-sensitive strategies to existing human rights norms and jurisprudence.

In spite of decades of discussions, there has been no consensus reached as to whether human environmental rights should be included into the human rights statute, and what appropriate legal tools are in place for enforcement. In 2019, UNEP and the UN Human Rights Office signed a new agreement, stepping up commitment to protect the rights of humans to a healthy environment, with UNEP’s Executive Director Inger Andersen declaring at the signing in Geneva that:

A healthy environment is vital to fulfilling our aspiration to ensure people everywhere live a life of dignity. We must curb the emerging trend of intimidation and criminalisation of land and environmental defenders, and the use of anti-protest and anti-terrorism laws to criminalise the exercise of rights that should be constitutionally protected.

On the same occasion, the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, Michelle Bachelet (2019) commented:

We call on leaders and governments to recognise that climate change and environmental degradation severely undermine the human rights of their people, particularly those in vulnerable situations – including the generations of tomorrow.

What the director of UNEP and the Human Rights High commissioner said was not much different from what was said in 1972 at Stockholm, or what has been repeated over and over since, or in keeping with the repeated theme of turning environmental human rights into a political issue. However, UNEP’s declaration has thrown in another dimension: the constitutional one. Environmental right as a constitutional right or instrument is nothing new to be repeated again, but what should and ought to be discussed is the validity of environmental constitutionalism in the environmental rights or human rights legal framework. While several countries have opted for including environmental protection in

their constitutions, the issues associated with human environmental rights appear to have been left out.

But the central point of all these conferences, discussions, and resolutions is that ignoring the environment in the short term may leave long term deleterious effects on humanity as a result of violation of human environmental rights.

Even if this reasoning is correct in cases of transboundary pollution affecting a neighbouring state, it does not follow that it will be equally valid in cases of global environmental harm, such as atmospheric pollution and climate change. Here the obvious problem is the multiplicity of states contributing to the problem, and the difficulty of showing any direct connection to the victims. For instance, Gonenc (2020) suggests framing environmental issues within human rights language, thus permitting environmental activists to bring these cases before regional human rights courts. However, one question that remains under-examined is what happens once frames belonging to one normative area are mobilized for political purposes in another normative area. However, and according to the earlier discussions of Cullet (1995) and Woods (2006), there exist diverging views on the extent to which using a human rights frame for environmental protection could be strategically advantageous. But what has not been tried cannot be deemed not to work.

The UN has not expressly recognized an environmental human right, but certain documents have made a connection between the environment and human rights. For example, the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (Adopted in 1990) expressly refers to environmental quality in Article 24 on the right to health. In addition, the Special Rapporteur of the United Nations Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities (UN-1999) has shown particular concern for the development of environmental human rights, and the concept has been discussed by Shelton (2002), with particular reference to the Commission's emphasis on the right to life and physical security, expressed in the UN Commission's statement:

The realization of the right to life, and to physical security and integrity is necessarily related to and in some ways dependent upon one's physical environment. Accordingly, where environmental contamination and degradation pose a persistent threat to human life and health, the foregoing rights are implicated.

However, the Commission's work and deliberations appear to have concentrated on Environmental Justice rather than Environmental Rights, accepting the fact that there is a thin line dividing the two issues in environmental law, but without rights, the question of justice becomes irrelevant.

One possible explanation for the reluctance of UN human rights institutions to engage more directly with human rights and the environment is probably due to their long-standing project on corporate responsibility for human rights abuses. While the primary responsibility for promoting and protecting human rights lies with the state, it has long been recognized that businesses and transnational corporations have contributed to or been complicit in the violation of environmental human rights in various ways, especially in developing countries. Developing countries lack the capacity to control foreign companies extracting natural resources in a manner that harms both the local population and the environment. Such a lack of capacity is mainly due to weak governments, poor or inadequate regulations, lax enforcement, corruption, or simply a too-close relationship between businesses and governments, which accentuates the problem in such countries.

Discussing ‘*Conceptualizing Norm Fusion through Environmental Rights*,’ Gonenc (2020) considers it as a process that may link norms belonging to two (or more) separate issue areas, ultimately resulting in a blended norm. However, Gonenc recognises that due to problems in the implementation of environmental human rights in a neoliberal economic framework and existing clashes between environmental and human rights norms, fusion between environmental and human rights norms remains contested. Or could it be another avenue to be explored and exploited by environmental human rights proponents?

On 10th December 2019, UNEP declared clean air as a human right, and Maria Cristina Zucca, Head of UNEP’s Pollution and Health Unit of the Chemicals and Health Branch states that:

Action is needed by decision-makers, the private sector and other key stakeholders to, on one hand, address pollution in its various forms, and at the same time, advance the promotion, protection and respect for environmental human rights,

In a 2019 report (A/HRC/40/55), the UN.HRC Special Rapporteur Dr. David R. Boyd explores the right to breathe clean air and the negative impact of air pollution on the enjoyment of many human rights. The Special Rapporteur highlights the different State obligations, which are both procedural and substantive, in relation to the right to breathe clean air, and makes a list of recommendations. In his report (A/HRC/40/55), the Special Rapporteur highlights the different State obligations, both procedural and substantive, in relation to the right to breathe clean air, and some of the ambitious actions recommended include:

- Monitoring air quality and health effects;
- Public reporting on air quality;
- Establishing air quality legislation, regulations and standards;
- Preparing air quality action plans;
- Implementing and enforcing air quality rules; and
- Evaluating and revising air quality standards and plans

The fact that UNEP (2019), the UN.OHCHRC (2019) and the UN.HRC (2021) recognise for the first time in the history of discussions regarding human environmental rights that a clean, healthy and sustainable environment should also be a fundamental human right does not, however, lead the finality of discussions about the stalemate any further. Both the Report and the Declaration is much more like recycling old ideas.

In any attempt to try and address the unresolved issues associated with human environmental rights, what needs to be urgently discussed both at national and international levels would be: *Can environmental human rights be devolved from ecological rights, or the rights of nature?* The interconnection is too strong for one to work without the other. Further, ramifications into other unresolved environmental law issues will have to be given the due consideration necessary. More importantly, the increase in environmental destruction and concomitant human rights violations requires that human rights law be extended to include environmental protections as a way to improve people’s lives through preservation of the environment. While international human rights law and environmental law have had a tendency to develop discrete but complex structures, recent efforts have seen international organizations concentrating on the intricate relationship that exists between human rights and environmental health in a number of treaties, covenants, and declarations, with the objective of developing these further into legally binding international instruments towards consolidating the human environmental rights proposal.

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